

NOTES

Studies on Hydrazones, Semicarbazones, Thiosemicarbazones and Oximes as Ligands. Part-VII: Some Divalent Metal Complexes of Benzalacetone Thiosemicarbazone

R. C. MISHRA and B. K. MOHAPATRA*

B. J. B. College, Bhubaneswar-751 014

and

D. PANDA

Department of Chemistry, S. C. S. College, Puri

Manuscript received 23 February 1982, revised 14 December 1982, accepted 19 March 1983

THIOSEMICARBAZIDE and thiosemicarbazone have attracted special attention due to their activity against virus, protozoa and certain kinds of tumour and also antitubercular activity. Drugs show increased activity when used in the form of their metal complexes and a number of metal chelates inhibit tumour growth. In the treatment of cancer also, the active species is not the thiosemicarbazone but its metal chelate. After Mashima's work¹, thiosemicarbazones have attained considerable importance as potential ligands in the synthesis of metal complexes.

Experimental

Benzalacetone thiosemicarbazone was prepared by the known method². Ethanolic solutions of different metal salts were treated with the ligand in 1 : 2 proportion and the solution refluxed for 30 min to 1 hr. The solution was reduced in volume by a rotary vacuum evaporator and kept standing in a refrigerator when crystalline compounds separated out. In some cases addition of petroleum ether was needed for the isolation of the complexes. Metal, halogen and thiocyanate were estimated as reported earlier. Conductance was measured in 10⁻³ M acetone solution of the complexes using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens at room temperature by Gouy method. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer, 621 spectrophotometer. Visible electronic spectra were recorded in 10⁻³ M chloroform solution of the complexes using Hilger-Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. Relevant analytical data are presented in Table 1 and some of the spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Manganese complexes are light yellow, cobalt complexes are brown or orange and nickel com-

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compounds	m.p. °C	Λ_M mhos. cm ²	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
				Metal	Halogen, thiocyanate or sulphur
1. MnLCl ₂	98	6.8	5.9	15.65 (15.98)	20.31 (20.68)
2. MnL(NOS) ₂	125	7.2	6.1	14.25 (14.09)	29.45 (29.75)
3. MnL(NO ₂) ₂	100	6.4	5.8	13.78 (13.91)	8.28 (8.10)
4. CoL ₂ Cl ₂	98	9.4	5.1	10.11 (10.38)	12.24 (12.50)
5. CoL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	112	8.5	5.2	9.25 (9.49)	10.16 (10.31)
6. CoL ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	107	8.2	4.9	8.31 (8.47)	9.04 (9.20)
7. NiL ₂ Cl ₂	115	11.2	3.2	10.05 (10.34)	12.22 (12.51)
8. NiL ₂ (NCS) ₂	101	10.8	3.3	9.35 (9.58)	18.81 (18.99)
9. NiL(NO ₂) ₂	92	12.5	—	14.28 (14.61)	28.62 (28.68)
10. NiL(ClO ₄) ₂	103	8.4	—	12.02 (12.32)	6.61 (6.71)
11. CuL ₂ Cl ₂	105	9.8	1.81	11.31 (11.10)	12.22 (12.41)
12. CuL ₂ (NCS) ₂	130	7.5	1.79	10.01 (10.29)	18.38 (18.78)
13. CuL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	125	6.8	1.82	10.23 (10.16)	10.42 (10.23)
14. CuL ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂	170	10.4	1.82	9.28 (9.07)	9.25 (9.13)
15. ZnLCl ₂	110	8.2	—	18.12 (18.40)	19.74 (19.98)
16. ZnL(NCS) ₂	100	7.9	—	16.08 (16.33)	28.78 (28.97)
17. [ZnL ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	105	252	—	9.14 (9.31)	9.24 (9.11)
18. CdL(NO ₂) ₂	140	12.4	—	24.38 (24.68)	6.82 (7.08)
19. [CdL ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	132	248	—	14.81 (15.0)	8.32 (8.54)

L = Benzalacetone thiosemicarbazone.

plexes are light green except the nitrate and perchlorate complexes which are deep yellow in colour. All the copper complexes are green and zinc and cadmium complexes are either white or yellowish white. The compounds are crystalline solids, fairly soluble in acetone in which medium they have low molar conductance values indicating non-electrolytic nature, excepting the zinc and cadmium perchlorate complexes which are 1 : 2 electrolytes.

Infrared spectra of benzalacetone thiosemicarbazone show main absorption bands at 3200, 1590, 980 and 755 cm⁻¹ region attributable to $\nu(\text{NH})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ vibrations, respectively. In the complexes, $\nu(\text{NH})$ remains almost unaffected except a slight shift to lower frequency region in the halide complexes possibly due to hydrogen bonding. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ invariably shifts to lower frequency region and is observed around 1575-1580

* To whom all correspondence should be directed.

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL DATA OF SOME COMPLEXES

Compound No.	Infrared Spectra (cm ⁻¹)					Electronic spectra $\nu_{\max}$ in kK (ϵ)
	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}=\text{S})$	
1	1575	720	1000	340	280	22.0(1), 22.4(2), 24.6(2)
4	1570	720	1000	330	290	19.0(38), 20.3
6	1575	725	995	335	290	19.2(35), 20.2
7	1570	720	995	325	295	9.5(7), 13.8(8), 24.6(12)
10	1575	720	1000	330	290	15.0(58)
12	1570	725	1000	335	295	13.8(45)
14	1575	720	990	340	290	14.3(48)
17	1570	725	1000	335	295	—
19	1575	720	1000	330	290	—

cm⁻¹ whereas $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ is found around 700 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. Thus, the ligand behaves as bidentate in all the complexes where bonding occurs through the azomethine nitrogen and thiocarbonyl sulphur atoms. This has been confirmed by the observation⁸ of $\nu(\text{M}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}=\text{S})$ around 325-340 and 280-295 cm⁻¹, respectively.

In the thiocyanato complexes, $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ is found around 2090 cm⁻¹ indicating⁴ the presence of terminal N-bonded thiocyanato group. Nitrate complexes show the ν_2 and ν_1 bands around 1420 and 1280 cm⁻¹ region and their difference of the order of 140 cm⁻¹ indicates^{5,6} monodentate nitrate group coordination. In case of zinc and cadmium perchlorate complexes one broad band is found around 1100 cm⁻¹ indicating^{7,8} ionic perchlorate group in conformity with their molar conductance data. Other perchlorate complexes exhibit three distinct bands in the 1000-1160 cm⁻¹ region confirming the covalent nature of perchlorate group in these compounds.

Visible electronic spectra of manganese complexes show three bands around 20.0, 22.4 and 24.6 kK attributable to ${}^6\text{A}_1 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_1$ (G), $\rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_2$ (G) and $\rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_1$ (G) transitions, respectively. The band positions and intensity values suggest⁹ a tetrahedral stereochemistry for these complexes. Cobalt complexes show the main band around 19.0 kK with a shoulder on the high frequency side attributable to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ transition, the shoulder being the consequence of splitting due to spin-orbit coupling. Thus the band positions, intensity and magnetic moment value support octahedral stereochemistry for the compounds. Nickel chloride and thiocyanato complexes exhibit three absorption bands around 9.5, 13.8 and 24.6 kK regions characteristic of octahedral stereochemistry in conformity with their magnetic moment values. Nickel nitrate and perchlorate complexes show one broad band at ~15.0 kK ($\epsilon=58$) supporting¹⁰ a square planar configuration of the complexes in agreement with their diamagnetic nature. In case of copper complexes one broad absorption band is observed around 13.8-14.5 kK region suggesting¹¹ a distorted octahedral configuration for these compounds. On the basis of analytical, conductance and infrared spectral data zinc and cadmium complexes appear

to have tetrahedral environment around the metal ions.

References

1. M. MASHIMA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1964, **37**, 974.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1971.
3. J. R. FERRARO, "Low Frequency Vibration of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum Press, New York, 1971.
4. A. TRAMER, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1962, **59**, 232.
5. R. V. BIAGETTI, W. C. BOTJER and H. M. HAENDLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 379.
6. A. B. P. LIEVER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 1042.
7. G. DWYER, J. G. HARTLEY and L. M. VENANZI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 1295.
8. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1963.
9. B. N. FIGGIS, "An Introduction to Ligand Fields", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1976.
10. H. G. GRAY and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **85**, 260.
11. G. A. AGAMBER and K. G. ORRILL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 897.

Synthesis and Spectral Studies on Complexes of *p*-Dimethyl Amino Anil of 3-Acetyl-4-Hydroxy Coumarin Glyoxal with Pt⁴⁺, Ir³⁺ and UO₂²⁺ Metal Ions

V. K. RASTOGI†, J. P. GOEL and B. S. TYAGI*

Department of Physics, Meerut College, Meerut-250 001 and

R. C. SAXENA and R. K. KELA

Department of Chemistry, M. M. (P. G.) College, Modinagar-201 204

Manuscript received 12 June 1981, revised 5 November 1982, accepted 28 April 1983

COUMARIN derivatives have found extensive application in medicine and biology and they are also known for their complex forming tendencies. We describe here the preparation and characterisation of complexes of *p*-dimethyl amino anil of 3-acetyl-4-hydroxy coumarin glyoxal with some third

† Permanent Address: Molecular Spectroscopy Research Laboratory, Department of Physics, Lajpat Rai College, Sahibabad-201 006.